

INTERNATIONALLY IMPORTANT STRATEGIC KEYPOINT OF THE TURKIC WORLD - ZANGEZUR CORRIDOR

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Annotation: *Zangezur, the ancestral land of Azerbaijan, is of historical, cultural and economic importance. With the help of the USSR, it was taken from Azerbaijan and given to Armenia at the beginning of the 20th century, the direct land connection with the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, which is currently an exclave of Azerbaijan, was cut off, and the unifying position of the Turkic world was also violated. Almost a century later, on September 27, 2020, as a result of the "44-day" war between Azerbaijan and Armenia, the Azerbaijani side achieved victory, and along with the liberation of the occupied territories, the "Trilateral" declaration of November 10, 2020 revealed the inevitability of opening the Zangezur corridor. The peace treaty initialed between Azerbaijan and Armenia on August 8, 2025 was an important step towards opening the corridor. In the present era, the Zangezur corridor will not only connect Azerbaijan with the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, but will also make a great contribution to the Turkic world by ensuring the development of Azerbaijan in the Caucasus. This article will discuss the history of Zangezur, its political, cultural and economic importance for the Turkic world in the modern era.*

Keywords: *Zangezur corridor, global trade corridor, strategic importance, Turkic world unity, regional transit.*

Introduction. Even after the Republic of Azerbaijan regained its independence on October 18, 1991, the post-Soviet period and the political tension it created have become the main problem of Azerbaijan to this day. It has always posed obstacles, especially in foreign policy. This tension began with the USSR's failure to give the historical lands of our Republic to Armenia. As a result, in the 1920s, the ancient lands of Azerbaijan were separated from Azerbaijan in various ways. One of these territories is the modern Western Zangezur territory. As if with the acquisition of this territory, the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic separated from the Republic of Azerbaijan, and the unity of the Turkic world was weakened.

Historical reference about Zangezur. Historical Azerbaijani lands, covering a wide geography from Derbent to Zanjan, from Kirkuk to Eastern Anatolia, were divided from time to time and settled within the borders of the modern Republic of Azerbaijan. The modern Azerbaijani state itself was divided into two parts with the occupation of Zangezur. Zangezur is one of the territories of Azerbaijan with a rich historical past. Zangezur covers an area of 7892 sq.km, consisting of the Gubadli, Lachin, Zangilan regions of Azerbaijan, and the Gafan, Gorus, Sisyan, and Megri regions of Western Azerbaijan, now called Armenia [1, p.6].

In antiquity and the early Middle Ages, the territory of Zangezur was part of the Mada kingdom, the Scythian kingdom, and the Atropatena state under the name of Syunik or Sisakan, and the Azerbaijani Albanian state. In the middle of the 6th century, as a result of the administrative reform of Khosrow Anushirevan I, the Adurbadagan province was created, and both northern and southern Azerbaijan were united under a single name. At the beginning of the 7th century, the victory of the Byzantine emperor Heraclius II in the war with the Sasanian shahenshah Khosrow Parviz II strengthened the tendencies for independence in the countries subject to Persian rule. As a result, the Syunik principality also became independent. Moisey Kalankatli in his work "History of Albania" notes the existence of an independent Syunik principality at the beginning of the 7th century. In

ancient sources, this region was called Sisakan or Syunik, and in Arab sources, Siojan. Researchers write that the toponym Sisakan is associated with the name of the Sakas, one of the ancient Turkic tribes living in that area. The Albanian historian Moisey Kalankatuklu in his work "History of Albania" provides information about the Albanian tribal associations living in this area, as well as about the Gargars, Khazars, Huns and other Turkic tribes [2, p.1]. As a result, these facts confirm the historical, ethnic, cultural and political belonging of the territory to the Azerbaijani people.

The Zangezur region was included in the historical and political geography of Azerbaijan for a long time. BC. Since the 4th century, the Zangezur region has been part of Caucasian Albania, and in later periods it was under the rule of the Arabs in the 7th–9th centuries, and the Sajids, Salaris, and Ravvadis, which existed in Azerbaijan in the 9th–11th centuries. In the 12th–early 13th centuries, the Azerbaijani Atabey state, in the 13th–14th centuries, the Hulaguds, and in the late 14th–early 15th centuries, the Jalairi and Temuri empires controlled this territory. In the 15th century, Zangezur was part of the Garagoyunlu and Aggoyunlu states. In 1590–1612 and 1724–1735, the region was under Ottoman rule, and during the khanates it was subordinated to the Karabakh Khanate. On the eve of the Russian occupation, Panah Khan incorporated the Zangezur territory into the Karabakh Khanate. After the occupation of Azerbaijan by Russia in the 1920s, the administrative division was changed and Zangezur was organized as the Zangezur district of the Ganja (Yelizavetpol) province, and was formed as a separate administrative unit in 1861. Since 1867, Zangezur district, with its center in Gorus, was included in the Yelizavetpol province and retained this status during the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic in 1918. As can be seen, Zangezur has always been part of the historical lands of Azerbaijan [1, p.7].

It should be noted that although Zangezur was used as the name of an administrative territorial division covering an entire zone from a geographical concept in the mid-19th century, the geographical concept of Zangezur was found as early as the 16th century. The Zangezur administrative-territorial unit was first mentioned separately in the document "Detailed Book of the Livas of Urud and Iskender Galasi" compiled by Ottoman officials in 1593 under the name "Zangezur District" [1, p.6]. As a result, we see that the history of the area has no connection or connection with Armenia. If we look at the policy pursued by Tsarism in particular, for example: with the creation of the Yelizavetpol Governorate in 1868, Zangezur was removed from the Shusha district and included in the governorate as a separate district together with the Mehri district, without taking into account existing ethnic and economic factors, aimed at undermining the unity of the Turkish-Muslim population at the expense of future Armenian immigrants. As a result of the resettlement policy of Tsarism, the number of Armenians increased rapidly, Turkish toponyms were subjected to Armenianization, and in 1905-1906, hundreds of innocent Turkish-Muslim people became victims of Armenian brutality. There are facts about this in the book "Bloody Years" by the Azerbaijani writer M.S. Ordubadi. In particular, there are facts about the events of Ohchu-Shabadek or Gafan Valley in Zangezur. For example: *"...On August 9, 1906, the population of four Muslim villages, while engaged in agricultural work, saw soldiers building fortifications on the tops of the mountains. Since they did not know their identity, representatives were sent to investigate the matter. Seeing military flags on the tops of the hills, the representatives approached them carelessly, mistaking these forces for government troops. However, when they advanced a little, they were fired upon by Armenian positions. As a result of the fire, it became clear that the people building the fortifications were Armenians. The villagers fled to their homes, armed themselves with old weapons, and took up defense. However, since the Armenians were equipped with modern weapons and the Muslims were mainly engaged in agriculture, the defense of the village became weak. As a result, strategic positions fell into the hands of the enemy..."* [3, p.103].

However, despite all this, if we look at the ethnic composition of Zangezur, even at that time the Turkish-Muslim population was the majority. In 1908, the population census documents for the Yelizavetpol province indicate that the population of Zangezur district was 294,753 people. Of these, 197,066 people (67%) were Muslims, 97,204 people (32.9%) were Armenian Gregorians, and 483 people (0.1%) were people of other religions [4, p.195]. Despite all this, if we look at the political

landscape of that time, as a result of World War I and the conditions it created in the region, we see the violence committed by Armenians against Azerbaijanis in 1918. As a result of the intervention of Andranik's troops in the region, the genocide of the Turkish Muslim population in Zangezur intensified, and Azerbaijanis were completely expelled from the western part of the district. For example, the report of the Extraordinary Commission of Inquiry states that 115 Muslim villages in Zangezur district were destroyed and wiped off the face of the earth by Armenians. The names of all the destroyed villages are listed in these documents. 3257 men, 2276 women and 2196 children were killed in 115 villages, 1060 men, 794 women and 485 children were injured. As a result, 10068 Azerbaijanis were killed or maimed in Zangezur district alone by the time the report of the commission was prepared [5, p.78]. The report stated that these terrible figures still do not provide complete information about the Armenian atrocities. Thus, many more Muslims became victims of Armenian atrocities.

Thus, as a result of the military and political processes taking place in the Zangezur region in 1918-1920, Armenia occupied the western part of Zangezur (Sisian, Gorus, Gafan and Mehri regions) covering 4505.5 sq. km. and in the following years was able to annex these regions to its territory. After the Sovietization of Armenia, the steps taken in late 1920 - early 1921 under the pressure of Bolshevik Russia to transfer Zangezur to Armenia resulted in the permanent loss of Western Zangezur. Out of more than 60 thousand Azerbaijani refugees expelled from Western Zangezur, only 5 thousand managed to return to their homeland. With the loss of Western Zangezur, the land connection between the main territory of Azerbaijan and its historical territory, Nakhchivan, was also eliminated. The Bolsheviks' transfer of Western Zangezur to Armenia was aimed not only at striking at the unity of Azerbaijan, but also at the unity of the entire Turkic world, and at dividing it geographically into two parts. The Soviet regime, not content with transferring Western Zangezur to Armenia, but also in order to increase the distance between Azerbaijan and Nakhchivan, significantly expanded the territory of Western Zangezur, which remained within it, by transferring many territories of Azerbaijan (11 villages of Nakhchivan and 16 villages of East Zangezur) to Armenia in the 1920s and 1930s. Of these villages, the entire village of Garchivan in Ordubad, part of the territory of the village of Kilit, as well as the villages of Nuvedi, Eynadzor and Tugut in Zangil were transferred to the newly created Mehri district [6, p.44].

The issue of the Second Karabakh War and the Zangezur Corridor came to the agenda. As is known, the occupation of Azerbaijani lands was not limited to these years, especially as a result of the further strengthening of Armenian territorial claims to Azerbaijan in the late 1980s, 20% of the lands of the Republic of Azerbaijan were occupied in 1992-1994. Approximately 30 years later, on September 27 - November 10, 2020, as a result of the 44-day war for the liberation of the occupied

lands of Azerbaijan, our lands were liberated from occupation, and as a result of the trilateral declaration signed on November 10, the opening of the Zangezur Corridor became necessary. The Declaration states that, “All economic and transport relations in the region are being restored. The Republic of Armenia guarantees the security of transport relations between the western regions of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic in order to organize the unhindered movement of citizens, vehicles and cargo in both directions. Control over transport relations is carried out by the Border Service of the Federal Security Service of Russia” [7].

Currently, an important factor playing a role in the opening of the Zangezur corridor is the signing of the “Joint Declaration” between the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev and the Prime Minister of the Republic of Armenia Nikol Pashinyan at a meeting held in Washington, United States of America on August 8, 2025. The Declaration reflected 7 main issues, especially Article 3 emphasized the opening of the Zangezur corridor. The Declaration states: “We, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Prime Minister of the Republic of Armenia, meeting on August 8, 2025 in Washington, D.C., United States of America, declare the following:

1. We and the President of the United States of America, Donald Trump, witnessed the initialing by the Foreign Ministers of the Parties of the agreed text of the “Agreement on the Establishment of Peace and Interstate Relations between the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Republic of Armenia.” In this context, we recognized the need to continue to take additional measures for the signing and eventual ratification of the Agreement and stressed the importance of ensuring and strengthening peace between our countries;

... 3. We reaffirmed the importance of opening communications between the two countries to ensure domestic, bilateral and international transport in order to promote peace, stability and prosperity in the region and its neighborhood, based on respect for the sovereignty, territorial integrity and jurisdiction of states. These efforts will ensure unhindered connectivity between the main part of the Republic of Azerbaijan and its Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic and international and includes mutual benefits for domestic connectivity;

4. The Republic of Armenia will cooperate with the United States of America and mutually determined third parties to define a framework for the “Trump Roadmap for International Peace and Prosperity” (TRIPP) connectivity project within the territory of the Republic of Armenia. We reaffirm our determination to make good faith efforts to achieve this goal as soon as possible”[8].

Problems and prospects for the implementation of the Zangezur corridor. Currently, there are three corridors in the world: the Northern, Southern and Central corridors. The Northern corridor connects China to Europe via Russia and takes an average of 20 days to travel. Due to cold weather

conditions, packaging and product loss costs arise due to freezing. The Southern corridor also starts from China and takes about 30 days to reach Europe by sea. The Central corridor starts from China and reaches Europe via Türkiye. This corridor takes an average of 12 days and is considered the best alternative compared to other routes. For all these reasons, the opening of the Zangezur corridor seems inevitable. The Zangezur corridor is a key link in the Middle Corridor. Compared to other alternatives (Northern and Southern corridors), the Middle Corridor is both safer and offers a shorter and more profitable route [13, p.21].

Although the importance of the Zangezur corridor is undeniable, the position of certain states regarding it is different. If we consider this from the point of view of the interests of the states of Russia, Iran and Georgia, the position of these states becomes clear, since the Zangezur corridor will result in a change in traditional trade routes. For example, if before the opening of the Zangezur corridor, the main transit routes passed through Russia, Iran and Georgia, then after the corridor is opened, Azerbaijan will play a special role in this matter. It is of strategic importance, especially in terms of the integration of regional transport and communication networks. Most importantly, it creates conditions for the expansion of economic and trade relations with Türkiye and the countries of Central Asia.

Among the interested parties in the opening of the Zangezur corridor, the Republic of Azerbaijan, the Republic of Türkiye, as well as the Turkic world as a whole should be noted. When the Shusha Declaration was signed between Azerbaijan and Türkiye, President Ilham Aliyev specifically touched upon this issue and said: *"The Declaration reflected very clear statements regarding the opening of the Zangezur corridor. This is also a result of the new geopolitical situation that emerged after the Second Karabakh War. Today, we are not only talking about the Zangezur corridor, which will connect Türkiye and Azerbaijan by rail and road, but we are creating this corridor through practical work. The reflection of this issue in the joint Declaration on Alliance signed is of great significance"* [9]. On the other hand, although the opening of the corridor limits the geopolitical influence of the regional states, it creates the opportunity to benefit from new transport and trade routes as a whole, which allows it to maintain its regional economic participation. Also, according to some experts, after the opening of the Zangezur corridor, the Chinese state will also be able to benefit significantly from this route. It is no coincidence that in an interview with a correspondent of the Chinese corporation "China Media Group", President Ilham Aliyev explained his views on the international importance of the Zangezur corridor as follows: *"... cooperation in transportation will be very beneficial for all countries, and at the same time, it is also important that these works will strengthen relations between countries. The countries will be more closely connected with each other, there will be integration. We plan to create many production areas along the corridor and do not want to be just a transit country. From a geopolitical point of view, this is a good thing, that is, additional income can be obtained, we want to create large industrial zones in Azerbaijan. In fact, we are moving in this direction. I believe that engaging in production in our Alat Free Economic Zone, which opened this month and has already started operating, can also be attractive for Chinese companies. In fact, it is a wider opportunity than you can imagine"* [9].

The importance of the Zangezur Corridor for the Turkic World. The South Caucasus has historically been a crossroads of trade routes along the east-west axis. The peace agreement initialed between Azerbaijan and Armenia in August 2025, mediated by the United States, has created a critical turning point in the geopolitical landscape of the region. At the heart of the agreement is the Zangezur Corridor, which connects Azerbaijan with the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. This corridor completes the Middle Corridor and paves the way for uninterrupted trade flows from Türkiye to China. With the opening of the Zangezur Corridor, the Azerbaijan-Türkiye land connection will also be restored. In fact, this is the most important issue for the Turkic World. Work is already underway on the roads to open the Zangezur Corridor. The length of the Zangezur Corridor here is 43 km. For future work, the Horadiz-Ordubad road, which has a total length of 166 km, will be laid, and then the 158 km Ordubad-Validag road is expected to be repaired and extended by 14 km and extended to Kars (Türkiye). The foundation stone of the Kars-Iğdır-Aralık-Dilucu railway line has already been

laid. Minister of Transport and Infrastructure Abdulkadir Uraloğlu stated that the 224-kilometer line is a key component of the Zangezur corridor, and that with the commencement of the Zangezur corridor, the east-west line stretching from Beijing to London will operate more efficiently; Turkey's logistics capabilities will increase, and the country's geostrategic position on trade routes to Asia will be strengthened [10].

Significant work is also being done in the territory of the Republic of Azerbaijan towards the opening of the Zangezur corridor, as the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev specifically noted in his joint press statement with the President of Kazakhstan Kassym-Jomart Tokayev in Astana on October 21, 2025: *“In addition to all the work that we are currently planning and implementing, the Zangezur Corridor project has great potential. All work related to automobile and railway infrastructure within Azerbaijan will be completed by the middle of next year. We hope that work will continue at the same pace in other countries, and in this case, the opening of the Zangezur corridor may take place by the end of 2028”* [12].

Along with the railway, work is also being done towards the construction of a land road. Of course, when all these processes are evaluated in the context of the opening of the Zangezur corridor, it will make a significant contribution to the acceleration of Azerbaijan's economic development in the region and the expansion of transport and trade infrastructure. At the same time, this corridor will strengthen economic, political and cultural integration between the countries of the Turkic world, increase their potential for strategic cooperation in the international arena and create conditions for the formation of new perspective opportunities. This corridor can also be seen as a bridge to the Turkic world. As the corridor is a key component of the Middle Corridor project, it provides an alternative route in Europe-Asia transport, thus reducing dependence on China-Russia routes - here, in particular, the European Union, Türkiye, Central Asian countries and China can be mentioned. Furthermore, if we look at the results of the 12th Summit of the Council of Heads of State of the Turkic States Organization, the Gabala Declaration states that the leaders expressed their support for the continuous efforts of the member states towards the launch and development of the Zangezur corridor and reaffirmed their commitment to fully exploiting the potential of the Baku-Tbilisi-Kars railway, emphasizing the importance of strengthening the Trans-Caspian International East-West China-Central China-Uzbekistan railway corridor and the interregional region [16].

The opening of the corridor is expected to significantly reduce trade distances between countries and increase trade. At the same time, it will eliminate the need for routes through countries such as Georgia and Iran, creating conditions for the direct transportation of goods to Azerbaijan and allowing for faster and more cost-effective transportation to Central Asia. This will increase the number of voyages in the Caspian Sea and potentially the functionality of ports. The People's

Republic of China, one of the world's most important exporters, annually supplies the global market with products worth \$ 2.4 trillion, half of which falls on the European market. In this context, China attaches great importance to economic relations with Europe and is interested in developing new alternative transport routes [14, p.6]. In addition, the increase in transport risks along the Northern Corridor after the outbreak of the Russian-Ukrainian war has further increased the strategic importance of the Middle Corridor. In addition to its economic attractiveness, the Middle Corridor offers a safer alternative route due to the geographical proximity of the countries in this corridor and their stable relations with other countries. On the other hand, this corridor offers China a politically strategic option, as it allows it to diversify its exports without using the Southern Corridor, reduce its dependence on Russia, the main player in the Northern Corridor, and safely send its products to Europe via Iran, which is under US sanctions [15, p.21]. By offering an alternative to the existing commercial transport network, China allows goods shipped from China to be delivered to the eastern provinces of Türkiye and from there to the rest of the world. In this regard, it can be predicted that the Zangezur corridor will become an important part of the global trade arena. The opening of the Zangezur corridor will also significantly contribute to the further development of trade and transport relations in the region, strengthening the economic integration of the Turkic states, whose nominal GDP is approximately 2.11 trillion US dollars (2024) [17].

Conclusion. The Zangezur corridor is of great importance in terms of restoring historical justice and ensuring the strategic unity of the Turkic world. The opening of the corridor, in addition to restoring land communication between Azerbaijan and Nakhchivan, optimizes Eurasian trade routes as the main link of the Middle Corridor. The project strengthens regional economic integration, increases the transit and production potential of Azerbaijan, and takes political and cultural cooperation between Turkic states to a new stage. In this regard, the Zangezur corridor plays the role of a strategic platform for both regional stability and global trade.

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